

Experiment on the phototaxis behavior of amphipod (*Niphargus* sp.)

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Abstract. For larvae of many biofouling organisms, the phototaxis behavior is crucial for their survival as it can help with their mobility, food searching and respond to danger. This experiment tested the phototaxis behavior of the adult of *Niphargus* sp. amphipod collected from Dapeng Shenzhen and compared it to the phototaxis behavior of the larvae of subtidal acorn barnacle in the genus *Balanus*. Result using four different wavelength of light shows that *Niphargus* sp. can sense and respond to lasers of 635, 532, 515 and 445 with negative phototaxis, very different from the phototaxis behavior of barnacle nauplius larvae. Despite both being in the same biofouling community, amphipods have more advance eye structure as well as more complex behavior than barnacle.

1. Introduction

For many relatively advanced organisms, phototaxis behaviors are crucial to their survival in nature. These behaviors allow them to tract food source, avoid predators, and function as indicators for time of reproduction. Phototaxis behavior is basically the sense and reaction to light, which could be either moving towards the light source, avoiding the light source, or no reaction. For the phototaxis behavior to occur, the organisms need to have visions that can sense light.

Because of these factors that determine the phototaxis behavior, different species with different niches can have different phototaxis behavior due to behavioral or biological difference. As an example, nauplius larvae of barnacles (*Balanus* sp.) are planktons that drift along with currents. Amphipods on the other hand are benthic. The difference in their size and ecological niche could result in different phototaxis behavior.

Amphipods are marine and freshwater shrimp like crustaceans that often make up an important part of benthic or biofouling communities. They have 8 pairs of legs, and they use the first 5 pairs of them to walk, and 3 pairs to thrust and swim. Amphipods vary a lot in size and shape, as some of them can grow to 30 cm while others are as small as grains. They usually feed on organic matters but don't mind hunting for plankton and creatures smaller than them. As relatively large organisms compared to other plankton, amphipods have well developed vision supported by a pair of compound eyes and a dozen single eyes. This setup allows Amphipod to detect most light sources and change in brightness.

According to research at the University of Florida (Smith and Whitman 1992), amphipods go through an incomplete metamorphosis life cycle [1]. Eggs are deposited within a brood pouch on the underside of the adult female amphipod's body. The eggs hatch in one to three weeks. The young amphipods resemble the adults and leave the pouch during the next one to eight days when the female has her first molt during mating. The molt usually takes about one hour. And most species complete their life cycle (egg to adult) in one year or less.

The target species used in this experiment belongs to the genus *Niphargus*.

Figure 1. A specimen of the *Niphargus* sp. used in the experiment, each scale beneath stands for a millimeter.

Niphargus is one of the largest genera of *Amphipoda*, species belong to this genus can be seen globally including China. *Niphargus* sp. usually live in freshwater or estuaries and can be found in soil or biofouling communities. The subject individuals in this experiment sizes between 0.3 to 1 centimeter (Figure 1). For this experiment Adult of this *Niphargus* sp. was obtained at Dapeng in Shenzhen in a biofouling biome. The GPS coordinate was 22°34'04.2"N 114°31'52.0"E.

The main goal for this experiment is to determine the phototaxis behavior of this *Niphargus* sp., whether it is negative, positive or no phototaxis to certain range of visible lights. The indication of phototaxis behavior can be related to its habits and the complexity of its vision. The behavior will be used to compare with the result of my previous experiment on the phototaxis behavior of barnacle larvae [2] as a reference to different phototaxis behaviors of lifeforms in Shenzhen biofouling communities.

2. Material and Method

At the sampling site, pH and salinity were tested. Samples of target species *Niphargus* sp. are obtained from biofouling surfaces at the sampling site. The specimen was then transferred to a plastic container filled with sea water obtained from the sampling site with oxygen pump. The samples were transferred and kept at the lab overnight. At 10 a.m. the next day, the sample was sorted out from debris and other biofouling organisms using straws and petri dish. The picture of the sample was taken with caution (Figure 1). The set up was composed of a rectangular 2*2*15cm container. The container was half filled with sea water from its sampling site. The container was then transferred under an infrared light camera with an infrared light generator. To most living beings, infrared light cannot be seen with naked eye, but specially designed camera can capture it, providing light source for video taking to be possible (Figure 2). The whole setup was put inside a dark box environment with no visible light. On one of the 2*2 sides of the container a stand with a laser pen was shot vertically through the middle of the container with a diffraction pad. After this the individual samples were added to the middle of the container, and the infrared light camera would record the behavior in the next 3 min.

For another set of experiments the same thing set up was used except the sample was added to the opposite site of the light source. No trace diagram was done for it because of difficulty in tracing movements.

In the experiments where sample started in the middle, the behavior of the amphipod was tested with laser pointers with wavelengths of 532nm, 635nm, 515nm, and 445nm. The resulting moving track was recorded and presented in this paper as a trace diagram. In this diagram the position of the sample was recorded for every 5 seconds from 0 to 2'30". The position of sample in the graph is indicated as its head, represented by dots. The dot-colored red indicates the initiate point of the sample, and green indicates the final position (Figure. 3).

3. Result

3.1 Specimen added at the side of the chamber

In the experiment using 635 nm (red light), the *Niphargus* sp. are added to the opposite side of the light source. The sample stay still for 36 second and then moves toward the light source for 1 cm, then slowly drift right 1.2 cm for the rest of the recording. The behavior is generally classified as no phototaxis behavior since the net movement of the sample is close to 0 and no significant locomotion.

In the experiment using 532 nm (green light), the sample stays still for 2 minutes 36 seconds and then moves toward the light source for 0.5 centimeter and stops for the rest of the time. The behavior is generally classified as no phototaxis behavior since the net movement of the sample is close to 0 and no significant locomotion.

In the experiment using 445nm (blue light), the sample stays still for 3 minutes and 16 seconds and then suddenly moves towards the light source till 4 minute and 40 second when it retreats for 3 cm and stays still. The result seems to be positive phototaxis because of net movement toward left, however the sample does show the behavior of avoiding light as it gets close to the light source.

In the experiment using 431nm (blue light), the sample is active in moving yet maintained at the opposite side of the light source for the whole recording. The result is considered no positive response to the light source since net movement of the sample is close to 0.

Figure 2. The experiment setting for the observation of phototaxis behavior of *Niphargus* sp.

3.2 Specimen added at the middle of the chamber

In the experiment using 635nm (red light), the *Niphargus* sp. went toward the red light slowly. After 45 seconds, the sample goes to the opposite side of the laser and stays there for 1 and a half minutes. The behavior is classified as negative phototaxis since the net movement of the sample is opposite to the light source and the end position of the larvae is in the right side of container (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Demonstration of the trace diagram. Notice that the light source always comes from the left side.

In the experiment using 445nm (blue light), the sample goes to the opposite side of the laser and stays there for the rest of the time. The behavior is generally classified as negative phototaxis since the net movement of the sample is opposite to the light source and the end position of the larvae is in the right side of container (Figure 3B).

In the experiment using 515 nm (green light), the sample goes to the opposite side of the light source and stays there for the rest of the time. The behavior is generally classified as negative phototaxis since the net movement of the sample is opposite to the light source and the end position of the larvae is in the right side of container (Figure 3C).

In the experiment using 532 nm (green light), the sample goes toward the light source for 5 seconds, then makes a sharp turn and goes to the opposite side of the light source, where it stays for the rest of the time. The behavior is generally classified as negative phototaxis since the net movement of the sample is opposite to the light source and the end position of the larvae is in the right side of container (Figure 3D).

In conclusion, it is identified that this *Niphargus* sp. can sense and respond to the most visible light with negative phototaxis. This means the sample avoided all wavelengths of light used in this experiment.

4. Discussion

Firstly, there are significant differences in the results obtained for experiment with the sample added to the middle and to the side. There are designing issues with experiments with the sample added to the opposite side. Since there is diffraction of laser by the material of the container, there is probably neglectable brightness difference at the very opposite side of the light source. Because of this it is inefficient to identify negative phototaxis behavior. However, neither result from both experiments conflicts with the conclusion. Although for the experiment with sample added to the middle, no negative phototaxis behavior can be detected, no positive phototaxis are presented either.

From the experiment data, it shows that this *Niphargus* sp. can identify most wavelengths of visible light at least from 650 to 445 nm. It also tends to avoid all light sources possible. Compared to the phototaxis behavior of the nauplius larvae of barnacle, there is a great difference. For the nauplius larvae of barnacles used in the previous experiment, there is a general positive phototaxis behavior detected with green, blue, and purple laser, while the plankton is not able to detect red light [2]. This significant difference may relate to differences in habitat, feeding behavior as well as biological complexity.

The experiment done before on the nauplius larvae of *Balanus* sp. shows positive phototaxis behavior for light within the wavelength of 405 to 532nm and shows no response to red light with wavelength of 635 and above [2]. This is because the sample used in the experiment was a couple times smaller than the amphipod, with no composed eye but only simple eye dots.

The sample of *Niphargus* sp. was found in small holes or gaps in the biofouling communities where light cannot shine on directly. This is to prevent the loss of water and body fluid and to avoid heat that could be potentially fatal. The same thing goes with amphipods and since they spend their entire lifecycle in biofouling community, they tend to avoid light. On the other hand, the nauplius larvae of barnacle are planktons that float freely in currents. They also depend on brightness to find their food source. Therefore, the nauplius larvae develop phototaxis behavior against most light sources except red light.

As for the eye structure, the nauplius larvae of barnacle consists of only simple eyes. They can identify brightness of most light source but can't respond to red light because of its biological simplicity as well as its habitat don't usually consist of this range of wavelength. However, the *Niphargus* sp. have well developed vision supported by a pair of compound eyes and a dozen other single eyes. This setup allows amphipods to detect most light sources and change in brightness, including red light since it lives close to surface level.

It is worth to note that the phototaxis behavior of amphipod may be different according to the specific environment its living in. For the experiment we used samples from biofouling communities, but amphipods have a wide range of habitat. They can be found in many places beside biofouling communities, and some of them do consist of different status. If more experiments can be done on the phototaxis behavior of other amphipod sp., it can help more with the accuracy and depth of the general phototaxis behavior of species that belong to the Amphipoda class.

References:

- [1] Smith EH, Whitman RC. 1992. Field Guide to Structural Pests. National Pest Management Association. Dunn Loring, VA.
- [2] Tong, H. (2022). Experiment on Phototaxis Behavior of Barnacle Larvae. *The Young Scientist*, 1(1), 9–16. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8048463>